

Revealing Thriving at work for better service quality of care in healthcare sector through Ambidextrous leadership and Job autonomy

Maria Younas*

PhD Scholar, Riphah School Of Leadership, Management Sciences Department, Riphah International Islamic University Email: mariayounas1986@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Muhammad Sarmad

HOD Riphah School Of Leadership, Management Sciences Department, Riphah International Islamic University Email: muhammad.sarmad@riphah.edu.pk

Rubina Awan

MS Riphah School of Leadership Management Sciences Department, Riphah International Islamic University Email: Riphah.rubiawaan863@gmail.com

Javeria Khalid

PhD Scholar, Riphah School Of Leadership, Management Sciences Department, Riphah International Islamic University Email: Khalid.javeria88@gmail.com

Author Details

Keywords: Ambidextrous Leadership, Thriving at Work, Job Autonomy, Service Quality of Care, Healthcare Professionals, Moderated Mediation, Pakistan.

Received on 15 May 2026

Accepted on 07 Jun 2026

Published on 19 Jun 2026

Corresponding E-mail & Author*:

Maria Younas*

PhD Scholar, Riphah School Of Leadership, Management Sciences Department, Riphah International Islamic University Email: mariayounas1986@gmail.com

Abstract

Service quality of care (SQC) is one of the key factors in effective healthcare and satisfaction of patients. Leadership behaviors are a crucial part of shaping employee behaviors and organizational outcomes in increasingly complex healthcare settings. Ambidextrous Leadership (AL) has been studied for its effects on exploration and exploitation behaviors, but its impact on the quality of healthcare services is still under-researched, notably through psychological mechanisms like Thriving at work (TAW) and contextual factors like Job Autonomy (JA). The current study was conducted to explore the impact of ambidextrous leadership on the quality of care of the healthcare workers in Pakistan. More specifically it examined the mediating role of thriving at work and the moderating role of job autonomy between the relationship between ambidextrous leadership and service quality of care. The research method was quantitative with a cross-sectional design. A structured questionnaire was used to gather data from 350 health care professionals, doctors and nurses from public sector hospitals of Pakistan. Ambidextrous leadership, thriving at work, job autonomy and service quality of care were measured using pre-existing scales. Direct, mediated and moderated mediation effects were tested using the PROCESS Macro (Model 14) implemented in SPSS. The results showed that the ambidextrous leadership positively and significantly influenced the variables of thriving at work ($\beta = 0.635, p < 0.001$) and thriving at work had a positive influence on service quality of care ($\beta = 1.127, p < 0.001$). Ambidextrous leadership and service

quality of care was significantly mediated by thriving at work. But, the direct path from ambidextrous leadership to the service quality of care was negative and significant ($\beta = -0.338, p < 0.001$). Additionally, job autonomy was found to significantly moderate all aspects of the relationship between thriving at work and service quality of care ($\beta = -0.079, p < 0.001$), suggesting that the positive indirect effect of leadership on service quality is weakened by increased levels of job autonomy. But job autonomy can diminish its positive effects on thriving on service quality, if it is too high. To maximize healthcare performance and outcomes, healthcare organizations should strive to foster ambidextrous leadership and balance employee autonomy.

Introduction

The quality of healthcare services is a crucial factor in the satisfaction of patients, the effectiveness of healthcare and the performance of the healthcare organization. Over the last few years, many health care systems have undergone major changes as a result of technological advances, growing populations, a rise in chronic illnesses and patients' expectations (Martínez-Climent *et al.*, 2019). These changes have created a significant strain on healthcare organizations to deliver quality, efficient and patient-focused healthcare services with limited resources and workforce capacity. Cai *et al.* (2023) predicted that the share of people aged 60 and older in the global population will grow significantly by 2050, leading to an increase in the demand for health care services. In the same manner, Ouyang *et al.* (2022) have highlighted the rising operational expenses, shortage of skilled healthcare workers and difficulties in providing sustainable healthcare services in health care systems. As a result, enhancing the quality of services is a key objective for healthcare providers around the globe.

To address these challenges, leadership has become an important consideration in the effectiveness of an organization and its healthcare outcomes. Leadership is crucial for healthcare professionals to effectively manage, enhance patient outcomes and promote adaptability within healthcare organizations in evolving environments (Zheng *et al.*, 2017). Traditional leadership styles tend to be either "steady as she goes" or "innovation and change. But leaders in today's healthcare landscape need to inspire innovation while also maintaining compliance with established processes and standards. This requirement has resulted in growing focus in Ambidextrous Leadership (AL) which is a leadership style that involves balancing exploratory and exploitative behaviors (Rosing *et al.*, 2011).

Ambidextrous leadership allows leaders to move between transformational and transactional leadership in response to the situation (Voigt, 2014). Transformational behaviour foster innovation, creativity and experimentation, while transactional behaviors focus on structure, control and alignment with organization objectives (Bucic *et al.*, 2010). In health care environments, leaders are often faced with both situations. Healthcare, for instance, has to adhere to stringent clinical standards at the same time being agile enough to meet new demands and innovations from patients. Thus, ambidextrous leadership could offer an effective platform to improve the quality of healthcare services through innovation and efficiency.

Organizational ambidexterity has received a significant amount of attention in recent years because organizations have to continuously exploit their capabilities while exploring for new opportunities to stay competitive and sustainable. Latham (2014) states that successful organizations find a balance between exploration and exploitation so that they can be successful in the long-term. Previous research has shown the positive impact of ambidextrous leadership in innovation and organizational performance, but there is a lack of research on ambidextrous leadership and its influence on healthcare service quality, especially in developing countries. The understanding of the ambidextrous leadership on the quality of service is thus crucial for healthcare organizations aiming to enhance patient outcomes and organizational effectiveness.

One key way that a leader might impact on the quality of the services is Thriving at Work (TAW). Work flourishing is a positive state of psychology that is comprised of vitality and learning (Spreitzer *et al.*, 2005; Porath *et al.*, 2012). Vitality involves the sense of energy, enthusiasm and aliveness, while learning involves ongoing growth and development of skills and knowledge (Nix *et al.*, 1999; Carver and Scheier, 1982). When employees feel vital and learning, they are more likely to show engagement, be adaptable, be creative and improve their performance. HCOs with a strong employee wellness program are more likely to help employees manage stress at work, adopt new clinical protocols and deliver better care outcomes to patients.

It is increasingly recognized that success in the workplace is important in health care settings. Martínez-Climent *et al.*, (2019) noted that employee well-being is closely related to service quality and organizational performance. Likewise, Cai *et al.* (2023) found a positive correlation between vitality and learning traits of healthcare professionals and their ability to provide better health care and reduce clinical errors. Although it is relevant, work success is under-researched in the health care field, especially as a pathway from leadership practices to service quality outcomes. Prior research has indicated that leaders are key in developing supportive contexts that encourage employee development and well-being (Spreitzer and Hwang, 2019). Thus, it is important that work thriving could be a significant mediator between ambidextrous leadership and service quality of care.

Job Autonomy (JA) is another important factor that affects the performance of employees and the quality of services. Job autonomy is the extent to which the employee is given freedom, discretion and independence in doing the job and in making decisions (Hackman and Oldham, 1975). Autonomy allows healthcare workers, such as doctors, nurses and healthcare professionals, to make decisions and take action to meet the needs of patients in clinical settings. Autonomy has been found to be positively related to job satisfaction, motivation, innovation and performance in a consistent pattern (Spreitzer, 1995). Autonomy of employees leads to higher level of commitment, better problem-solving skills and higher responsibility for the organizational goal (Dhar, 2016).

Prior research also has shown that autonomy can have a beneficial impact on service quality and work outcomes (Gellatly and Irving, 2001; Langfred and Moye, 2004). Healthcare units with higher levels of autonomy had higher patient satisfaction ratings and fewer clinical errors, as found by Ouyang *et al.* (2022). Second, autonomy might reinforce the positive influence of thriving at work by providing opportunities for employees to use their knowledge, skills and creativity better. Thus, job autonomy could moderate this relationship between thriving at work and service quality of care. Although there is increasing research interest in the relationship between leadership and employee well-being, there are still significant research gaps. Most research on ambidextrous leadership has focused on business and organizational settings and there has been relatively little research on ambidexterity in healthcare (Hafeez *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, the majority of previous research has examined direct links between leadership and performance and excluded psychological processes that link leadership to performance. Spreitzer and Hwang (2019) highlighted the importance of additional research into the relationship between leadership practices and the thriving of employees and the effectiveness of organizations. In the same way, though job autonomy has been linked to positive work outcomes, few studies have investigated the possible moderating effect on the relationship between thriving at work and service quality.

The issues of long wait times, poor communication, limited resources and varying service quality remain key areas of concern in healthcare organizations, particularly in Pakistan. Some research has indicated that patient dissatisfaction may be linked to treatment delays, lack of communication and negative staff attitudes (Dansereau *et al.*, 2015). Although the role of healthcare professionals is crucial for determining service

quality, there is a scarcity of empirical studies that investigate the combined effect of leadership, employee thriving and autonomy on healthcare outcomes within the Pakistani context.

Hence, the current study seeks to examine and explore Ambidextrous Leadership, Thriving at Work, Job Autonomy and the Service Quality of care of the healthcare professionals in Pakistan. In particular, the study investigates the interrelationships between ambidextrous leadership and service quality, the effect on service quality of the mediator thriving at work and the moderator job autonomy. This study adds to the literature on healthcare leadership and organizational behavior and offers practical implications for healthcare administrators and policymakers who aim to enhance the quality of care and the well-being of their staff.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

A quantitative cross-sectional research design was used to explore the relationships between Ambidextrous Leadership (AL), Thriving at Work (TAW), Job Autonomy (JA) and Service Quality of Care (SQC) among healthcare professionals in Pakistan. Quantitative study is commonly used to examine the relationships between variables, by systematically collecting and statistically analyzing numerical data (Biesta, 2024). A cross-sectional survey approach was thought to be suitable as it would enable the collection of data from a large sample of respondents at one point in time and provide the opportunity to examine associations between variables in the study efficiently.

A structured questionnaire was used to gather data, using four scales to measure respondent perceptions about leadership practices, thriving at work, job autonomy and service quality. Survey was chosen for its ability to collect data in a reliable and standardized way from health care professionals working in a variety of organizational settings. Before the data was collected, participants were told their responses would be anonymous and confidential and why we were conducting the study. No one was forced to participate and informed consent was obtained from all who participated.

Population and Sample

The study considered frontline healthcare workers (MBBS doctors and registered nurses) working in public-sector hospitals throughout Pakistan as the target population. The selection of these professionals was based on their direct involvement in patient care and service delivery, which provides them with a unique perspective on the leadership behaviors exhibited and the outcomes of service quality in healthcare organizations. The number of respondents in the study is 350. The regression and moderated mediation analyses had an adequate sample size and statistical power to detect significant relationships between the study variables. The respondents included a wide variety of health care institutions and health care professions, which increased the generalizability of the results in the public health care system.

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used was non-probability purposive sampling technique. This sampling method was deemed suitable since the study specifically looked at health care professionals with relevant experience on leadership practices, autonomy at work and care practices. The doctors and nurses were purposively selected because they were easily accessible, willing to participate and directly involved in healthcare service delivery. Purposive sampling facilitated the researcher to gather context information from the people who know the phenomenon being studied. Even though probability sampling techniques might be more representative, there are times when researchers in organizational and health care studies need a sample of individuals who have special knowledge and experience and so purposive sampling is used.

Measurement Scales

Previously validated scales, adapted from the literature were used for all study variables. A 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree was used for determining the level of agreement with the respondents.

Ambidextrous Leadership (AL)

Ambidextrous Leadership was assessed with a 13 item scale created by Rosing *et al.* (2011). The scale measures both exploratory and exploitative as well as opening and closing behaviors of leadership. Examples of items were: “Allows different ways to accomplish tasks” and “Encourages experimentation with new ideas.” The higher the score, the more the ambidextrous leadership behavior was perceived.

Thriving at Work (TAW)

The 9-item scale developed by Porath *et al.* (2012) was used to evaluate the Thriving at Work. The scale consists of two aspects to thriving: vitality and learning. Learning is a measure of ongoing growth and mastery while Vitality is one of energy and enthusiasm. Sample items were statements pertaining to personal development and to feeling energized at work.

Job Autonomy (JA)

Job Autonomy was assessed with the 4-item scale created by Beehr (1976). The scale measures the amount of independence and discretion enjoyed by employees in the execution of their tasks. Examples of these items were “I control the content of my job” and “I have the authority to initiate projects at my workplace.” In this study, higher scores indicated higher perceived autonomy.

Quality of care provided by services

The Service Quality of Care was assessed using a 5-item scale adapted from Slåtten *et al.* (2009) and confirmed by Slåtten and Lien (2023). The scale measured the respondents' perception of the quality of healthcare that they offer. Items to capture important dimensions of quality healthcare services were developed, such as empathy, timeliness, consistency and conformance to clinical standards.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Hayes' PROCESS Macro (Version 4.0). The dataset was screened for missing values, coding errors and assumptions of normality before the hypothesis testing. Descriptive statistics were used to describe respondents' characteristics and variables in the study. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were used to test internal consistency of the measurement scales. Correlation analysis was used to investigate the existence of strong and direction relation between Ambidextrous Leadership, Thriving at Work, Job Autonomy and Service Quality of Care. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the direct effects postulated in the conceptual framework. Moreover, the moderated mediation analysis was performed using PROCESS Macro Model 14 (Hayes, 2022). This model was chosen because it can be used to investigate mediation and moderation at the same time.

The analysis focused on: (1) the direct relation between Ambidextrous Leadership and Thriving at Work and Service Quality of Care, (2) the mediation of Thriving at Work between Ambidextrous Leadership and Service Quality of Care and (3) the moderation of Job Autonomy between Ambidextrous Leadership and Thriving at Work and Service Quality of Care. The interactions between Thriving at Work and Job Autonomy were also examined. Demographic variables, including age, gender, professional role and work experience, were also included as control variables to reduce possible confounding effects. Confidence intervals and indirect effects were estimated using bootstrapping procedures with 5,000 resamples and statistical significance was tested at the 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$).

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

In this research, a total of 350 healthcare professionals (HCP) from public sector hospitals in Pakistan were included. Demographic characteristics included age, gender, work position and working experience. The age group with the highest population was 25–34 years (34.3%) followed by 35–44 years (27.4%). The age group 18–24 years and 45–54 years had 14.6% each while the age group 55–64 years and above had 9.1%.

The age distribution suggests that most of the participants were at a relatively young age and in the early to middle stages of their careers, potentially impacting their perceptions of leadership practices, autonomy and workplace thriving. There were approximately equal numbers of males (52%) and females (48%) who responded. This sort of representation of the responses helps to increase the generalizability of the results to both genders. Professional occupations included nurses (36.3%), doctors (26.9%), technicians (14%), administrative staff (12%) and pharmacists (2.3%) along with other health care workers. This distribution allowed representation by various healthcare disciplines and ensured a well-rounded assessment of healthcare service delivery perspectives.

The participants also ranged in experience. About 24.9% had between one and three years of experience and 44.3% had seven or more years of professional experience, of which 21.4% had more than fifteen years of service. This diversity enabled this study to gain insight from the views of both new and old healthcare professionals.

Figure 1: Demographic Characteristics of Healthcare Professionals Participating in the Study.

Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to test internal consistency of the measurement scales for reliability analysis. Results showed that all constructs were satisfactory for reliability. Ambidextrous Leadership demonstrated high reliability ($\alpha = 0.958$) as did Thriving at Work ($\alpha = 0.926$). Job Autonomy had good reliability ($\alpha=0.817$) and Service Quality of Care had acceptable reliability ($\alpha=0.786$). These results show that all scales were reliable and appropriate for further analysis.

Figure 2: Reliability Analysis of Study Constructs Based on Cronbach's Alpha Values

Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation was done to explore the relationships between variables of the study. Ambidextrous Leadership was highly positively associated with Job Autonomy ($r = .906, p < .01$) and Thriving at Work ($r = .869, p < .01$). Similarly, Autonomy of Work was found to be positively correlated with Thriving at Work ($r = .770, p < .01$). However, Ambidextrous Leadership and Thriving at Work were both negatively related to Service Quality of Care ($r = -.202, p < .01$; $r = -.254, p < .01$, respectively). There was no statistically significant relationship between Job Autonomy and Service Quality of Care ($r = -.071, p > .05$).

Note: AL, JA, and TAW correlations are positive; SQC-related correlations are negative in bivariate analysis.

Figure 3: Correlation Matrix Showing Relationships Among Ambidextrous Leadership, Job Autonomy, Thriving at Work and Service Quality of Care

Hypothesis Testing

Hayes' PROCESS Macro Model 14 was used to test hypotheses. Ambidextrous Leadership (AL) was specified as the independent variable, Thriving at Work (TAW) as the mediator, Service Quality of Care (SQC) as the dependent variable and Job Autonomy (JA) as the moderator.

This first regression model was focused on the effect of AL on TAW. The model was highly significant and explained 75.71% of the variance in TAW ($R^2 = .7571$). Hypothesis 2 was supported as Ambidextrous Leadership positively predicted Thriving at Work ($\beta = 0.6347$, $p < .001$).

The second regression model was used to evaluate the predictors of Service Quality of Care. The model was statistically significant, $F(8,341) = 13.94$, $p < .001$, explaining 24.6% of the variance in SQC. Thriving at Work had a positive effect on Service Quality of Care ($\beta = 1.1265$, $p < .001$) as was hypothesized (Hypothesis 3). However, Ambidextrous Leadership had a statistically significant negative direct link to Service Quality of Care ($\beta = -0.3383$, $p < .001$) which led to the rejection of Hypothesis 1.

Figure 4: Direct Effects of Ambidextrous Leadership, Thriving at Work and Job Autonomy on Service Quality of Care

Moderation and Moderated Mediation Analysis

The interaction effect of Thriving at Work and Job Autonomy was significant ($\Delta R^2 = .1009$, $F = 45.68$, $p < .001$), suggesting that the relationship between Thriving at Work and Service Quality of Care was moderated by Job Autonomy. Conditional effect analysis revealed that Thriving at Work had a strong positive effect on Service Quality of Care at low levels of Job Autonomy ($\beta = 0.4251$). But, at medium autonomy ($\beta = 0.1913$) and at high autonomy ($\beta = -0.1204$), the effect weakened and reversed, respectively. This means that very high levels of autonomy could dilute the positive effects of flourishing on service quality.

The conditional indirect effects also revealed that the mediation by Thriving at Work was different based on the Job Autonomy levels. Indirect effect (through TAW) of AL on SQC was positive and significant at low autonomy (Effect = 0.2698). For moderate autonomy, the indirect effect was also positive, but less so (Effect = 0.1214). The indirect effect was negative (Effect = -0.0764) at high autonomy. The Index of Moderated Mediation was significant (Index = -0.0495 , 95% CI = $-0.0647 - -0.0353$), which means that Job Autonomy significantly moderated the indirect path from AL to SQC through TAW.

Figure 5: Conditional Effects of Thriving at Work on Service Quality of Care Across Different Levels of Job Autonomy

Figure 6: Conditional Indirect Effects of Ambidextrous Leadership on Service Quality of Care Through Thriving at Work at Different Levels of Job Autonomy

Figure 7: Index of Moderated Mediation for the Relationship Between Ambidextrous Leadership and Service Quality of Care

Hypotheses 2, 3 and 4 are supported and Hypotheses 1 and 5 are not supported. Results show that Ambidextrous Leadership has a positive indirect effect on Service Quality of Care via Thriving at Work and that greater Job Autonomy has a negative indirect effect.

Discussion

The present study analyzed Ambidextrous Leadership (AL), Thriving at Work (TAW), Job Autonomy (JA) and Service Quality of Care (SQC) among healthcare professionals (HCP) in Pakistan. The results offer valuable insights into the relationship between leadership practices and outcomes of healthcare services.

Results showed that Ambidextrous Leadership had a significant and positive impact on Thriving at Work ($\beta = 0.6347$, $p < .001$), thus supporting Hypothesis 2. This is in line with earlier research showing that leaders who are able to balance exploratory and exploitative behavior provide work environments where employees feel vital, learn and are engaged (Rosing *et al.*, 2011; Zacher and Rosing, 2015). In healthcare environments, this kind of leadership stimulates the adaptability of workers to new or shifted clinical needs and allows the organization to run efficiently. Thus, ambidextrous leaders seem to be able to create an environment that is psychologically supportive to allow health care professionals to continue to flourish in the face of limited resources and pressures at work.

The findings also showed that the Thriving at Work variable significantly influenced the Service Quality of Care ($\beta = 1.1265$, $p < .001$), which was in line with Hypothesis 3. This is in line with Spreitzer *et al.* (2005) and Porath *et al.* (2012) who supported that flourishing workers possess a higher adaptability, resilience and dedication to the company's objectives. Vitality and lifelong learning among healthcare professionals are more likely to result in healthcare services of high quality, responsive and patient-centred. Thus, employee thriving is an important psychological asset that directly relates to the quality of healthcare services.

Contrary to the expected, it was found that Ambidextrous Leadership has a significantly negative direct effect on Service Quality of Care ($\beta = -0.3383$, $p < .001$) so that Hypothesis 1 is rejected. This finding contradicts previous research which showed a positive direct impact of ambidextrous leadership on organizational performance and service results (Rosing *et al.*, 2011; Bucic *et al.*, 2010). One possible reason is the presence of highly bureaucratic and protocol-based environment in the public-sector healthcare organizations in Pakistan. Changing from one type of leadership (transformational) to the other (transactional) often leads to confusion on the part of employees and this can lead to less uniformity in service provision. According to Brek-Karama, (2024), the effectiveness of leadership is significantly shaped by the organizational context, meaning that what works in one setting might not necessarily work in another.

Hypothesis 4 was supported, as the mediation analysis revealed that the relationship between Ambidextrous Leadership and Service Quality of Care was significantly mediated by Thriving at Work. The positive indirect effect indicates that leadership improves service quality mainly by being able to boost employee vitality and learning. In line with the Job Demands–Resources framework, which posits that supportive leadership serves as a job resource that helps to foster positive psychological states and better performance outcomes (Gerlach *et al.*, 2020), this finding corroborates that supportive leadership is a job resource. Therefore, flourishing is an important pathway by which leadership can impact on healthcare.

A surprising outcome of the moderation analysis was observed. Interestingly, Hypothesis 5 was not supported; the positive association between Thriving at Work and Service Quality of Care was significantly weakened by Job Autonomy ($\beta = -0.0779$, $p < .001$). While previous studies have shown that there is a general link between autonomy and higher levels of motivation and performance (Deci and Ryan, 2000;

Dhar, 2016), this study has indicated that sometimes autonomy can be too much in healthcare settings. Healthcare workers at higher levels of autonomy might stray from the standard clinical routine, which could lead to a decrease in uniformed care and quality. This discovery validates the notion of structured autonomy, which refers to giving workers autonomy to make decisions, while ensuring they are still following professional guidelines and organizational protocols (Breevaart *et al.*, 2014). The results contribute to Ambidextrous Leadership Theory and Self-Determination Theory by showing that leadership effectiveness is related to employee thriving and that the positive outcomes of autonomy are still context-specific. The findings underscore the need to promote employee well-being as a means to enhance the quality of healthcare services.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to observe the impact of Ambidextrous Leadership, Thriving at Work and Job Autonomy on Service Quality of Care of healthcare professionals in Pakistan. The results revealed that Ambidextrous Leadership significantly contributes to Thriving at Work and that in turn, Thriving at Work contributes significantly to Service Quality of Care. Moreover, it was concluded that Thriving at Work is a mediator between Ambidextrous Leadership and Service Quality of Care, meaning that leadership fosters better healthcare outcomes by helping to create employee vitality and learning. Ambidextrous Leadership actually had a negative direct impact on Service Quality of Care, which implies that there may be context and/or organizational factors that affect the effectiveness of leadership. Further, Job Autonomy did not support the association between Thriving at Work and Service Quality of Care, as high levels of autonomy may lead to less follow-up of standard care in healthcare. Such results highlight the need to combine employee empowerment with the necessary organizational controls. The study's findings are that healthcare organizations can enhance service quality by fostering a flourishing workplace through adaptive leadership. Enhanced ambidexterity of leadership and the establishment of a structured autonomy system could positively impact employee wellbeing, healthcare service provision and potentially improve patient outcomes in Pakistan's healthcare system.

References

- Beehr, T. A. (1976). Perceived situational moderators of the relationship between subjective role ambiguity and role strain. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 61(1), 35-40.
- Biesta, G. (2024). Taking education seriously: The ongoing challenge. *Educational Theory*, 74(3), 434-448.
- Breevaart, K., Bakker, A. B., Hetland, J., Demerouti, E., Olsen, O. K. and Espevik, R. (2014). Daily transactional and transformational leadership and daily employee engagement. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 87(1), 138–157.
- Brek-Karama, F. (2024). The effect of ambidextrous leadership, innovation work behavior and job autonomy on employee performance. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 12(10), 1-15.
- Bucic, T., Robinson, L. and Ramburuth, P. (2010). Effects of leadership style on team learning. *Journal of Workplace learning*, 22(4), 228-248.
- Cai, Y., Li, Q., Cao, T., Wan, Q., 2023. Nurses' work engagement: The influences of ambidextrous leadership, clinical nurse leadership and workload. *J Adv Nurs* 79. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15086>

- Carver, C. S. and Scheier, M. F. (1982). Control theory: A useful conceptual framework for personality-social, clinical and health psychology. *Psychological Bulletin*, 92, 111–135.
- Dansereau, E., Masiye, F., Gakidou, E., Masters, S. H., Burstein, R. and Kumar, S. (2015). Patient satisfaction and perceived quality of care: evidence from a cross-sectional national exit survey of HIV and non-HIV service users in Zambia. *BMJ open*, 5(12), e009700.
- Deci, E. L. and Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268.
- Dhar, R. L. (2016). Ethical leadership and its impact on service innovative behavior: The role of LMX and job autonomy. *Tourism Management*, 57, 139–148.
- Gellatly, I. R. and Irving, P. G. (2001). Personality, autonomy and contextual performance of managers. *Human performance*, 14(3), 231-245.
- Gerlach, F., Hundeling, M. and Rosing, K. (2020). Ambidextrous leadership and innovation performance: a longitudinal study. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 41(3), 383-398.
- Hackman, J. R. and Oldham, G. R. (1976). Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 16(2), 250-279.
- Hafeez, M., Panatik, S. A., Rahman, A. A. A., Rajab, A., Bakar, S. A. and Norazman, I. (2019). Ambidextrous leadership and innovative work behavior: mediating role of emotional intelligence. *Int J Recent Technol Eng*, 8(2), 906-910.
- Hayes, A. F. (2022). Introduction to mediation, moderation and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach (3rd ed.). The Guilford Press.
- Langfred, C. W. and Moyer, N. A. (2004). Effects of task autonomy on performance: an extended model considering motivational, informational and structural mechanisms. *Journal of applied psychology*, 89(6), 934.
- Latham, J. R. (2014). Leadership for quality and innovation: Challenges, theories and a framework for future research. *Quality Management Journal*, 21(1), 11–15.
- Martínez-Clement, C., Rodríguez-García, M., Zeng, J., 2019. Ambidextrous leadership, social entrepreneurial orientation and operational performance. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 11.
- Nix, G. A., Ryan, R. M., Manly, J. B. and Deci, E. L. (1999). Revitalization through self-regulation: The effects of autonomous and controlled motivation on happiness and vitality. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 35(3), 266–284.
- Ouyang, C., Zhu, Y., Ma, Z., 2022. Ambidextrous Leadership and Employee Voice Behavior: The Role of Work Motivation and Ambidextrous Culture. *Psychol Res Behav Manag* 15.
- Porath, C., Spreitzer, G., Gibson, C. and Garnett, F. G. (2012). Thriving at work: Toward its measurement, construct validation and theoretical refinement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 33(2), 250-275.
- Rosing, K., Frese, M. and Bausch, A. (2011). Explaining the heterogeneity of the leadership-innovation relationship: Ambidextrous leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 22(5), 956–974.
- Slåtten, T. (2009). The effect of managerial practice on employee-perceived service quality: The role of emotional satisfaction. *Managing Service Quality*, 19(4), 431–455.
- Slåtten, T., Mutonyi, B. R., Nordli, A. J. and Lien, G. (2023). The role of ambidextrous leadership and employee ambidexterity in enhancing service quality of care and creativity—a study of health professionals. *BMC health services research*, 23(1), 1252.

- Spreitzer, G. M. (1995). Psychological empowerment in the workplace: Dimensions, measurement and validation. *Academy of management Journal*, 38(5), 1442-1465.
- Spreitzer, G. and Hwang, E. B. (2019). How thriving at work matters for creating psychologically healthy workplaces: Current perspectives and implications for the new world of work. *Creating psychologically healthy workplaces*, 293-310.
- Spreitzer, G., Sutcliffe, K., Dutton, J., Sonenshein, S. and Grant, A. M. (2005). A socially embedded model of thriving at work. *Organization Science*, 16(5), 537–549.
- Voigt, T. (2014). Ambidextrous leadership in innovation management processes: exploring the dynamics of opening and closing leadership behaviors at different levels of the stage-gate model (Master's thesis, University of Twente).
- Zacher, H. and Rosing, K. (2015). Ambidextrous leadership and team innovation. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 36(1), 54–68.
- Zheng, J., Wu, G., Xie, H., Xu, H., 2017. Ambidextrous leadership and sustainability-based project performance: The role of project culture. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 9.